

HARMONISING THE ECONOMIC RATIONAL BETWEEN CONSUMER'S RIGHT AND COMMERCIAL INTEREST IN THE CONTEMPORARY BROADCASTING INDUSTRY

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Abstract: This paper examines “Consumers’ Right and Commercial Interest: Balancing the Economic Equation”. It is a descriptive and analytical paper which seeks to know whether the broadcast media industry in Nigeria are fulfilling their social responsibility to the public as well as the consequence of commercialisation on the consumers; and conflict between the broadcast media commercial interest and obligation to the consumer. There is no doubt, the deregulation of the broadcast media and the subsequent commercialisation and liberalisation of the media landscape opened a new vista for broadcasting in Nigeria to the benefit of few and the detriment of the consumer who does not have the clout to determine what goes into the media either through participation or access. The consumer has become the guinea pig sold to advertisers who can afford the high and exorbitant media charges. The consequence is that since he who pays the piper dictates the tune; the consumer’s right to be informed, educated, entertained and communicate through the broadcast media is trampled on. This is not good for the broadcast media industry since the consumer is one of the most important factors in the survival and existence of the media, thus the increasing need to steer a middle course by giving the consumer his due. The Social Responsibility Theory and the Democratic Participant Theory provided the theoretical underpinning for this paper.

Keywords: consumer, commercial interest, economic equation, public interest, commercialisation

Introduction

One dominant trend pervading the entire broadcast spectrum whether it is public or private broadcast media is hyper-commercialism; which is a term that is used to describe the increasing commercialisation of media activities. The broadcast media are now commercial-oriented. In recent years, media programmes have become dominated by commercials.

Radio and television programmes are now dominated by advert messages of companies who intend to sell their goods and services to the audience members. Because there is limited funding, both in government and private media, they are forced to make money themselves through advertising. This explains why television and

radio programmes are dominated by advertising messages.

National Broadcasting Code (2010, p.54), stipulates that the total time for advertisement materials shall not exceed six minutes in a 30-minute programme and twelve minutes in a 60-minute programme. The code added, such advertisement materials shall be in 15 seconds, 30 seconds, 45 seconds and 60 seconds spots. But this rule is kept in the breach. Advert messages in the broadcast media are aired as many times as possible in a single programme. Most times when a programme is on radio or television, you even wonder whether it is the advertising message you are watching or listening to. However, media organisations argue that advertising is one of the major sources of generating revenue in the

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media. Private media organisations rely on advert to generate funds for survival. They have no choice other than to pay attention to advert messages because of poor funding, the increasing need to fulfil their obligation to employees, take care of their production and broadcast equipment and in some cases, they have to rely on advertising as a means of generating funds to meet their financial needs or obligations. It is in line with the above situation that Baran (2002) cited in Asemah (2011, p.29) observes that:

“the cost involved in acquiring numerous or larger media outlets, domestic and international and of reaching an increasingly fragmented audience must be regained somehow. Selling more advertising on existing and new media and identifying additional ways to combine contents and commercials are the most common strategies.”

What this means is that the rise in the number of commercial minutes can be associated to the fact that the media need to recoup their investment. Over dependence on commercialisation poses grave danger to the integrity of the media themselves and disservice to their audiences while those who are in favour of it see it as the economic reality of today’s media.

Until the deregulation of broadcasting in 1992, broadcasting in Nigeria has been the exclusively under the government’s domain. It played important role in national building and development. The Nigeria’s broadcasting programmes were modelled after the BBC in addition to news with tailored thematic areas such as children, current affairs, education, religion, and sports (Kolade, 1974). However, the 1992 deregulation through Decree No. 38 of 1992 helped in the establishment of the Nigeria Broadcasting Commission (NBC), and invested in them the power to control all broadcasting in the country. This led to the establishment of other stations owned by private individuals or organisations. The importance of this is that private participation has helped to expand the scope of the media as a forum for public education (enlightenment), information (awareness), and entertainment (amusement), these media trends are believed to be “promoting a continuation of the shift

away from involving people in societies as political citizens of nation states towards involving them as consumption units in a corporate world” (Golding and Murdock, 2000:77-78). This liberalization of the sector by bringing in the private sectors has increased the commercialisation drive thereby forcing the traditional public service broadcasters to extend their broadcast time and adjust their programming (Hulten and Brants, 1992; Betiang, 2004). However, in the process of extending programmes to compete, public service broadcasters tried to make some of their programmes attractive to advertisers, while those that are not so attractive, no matter who and what issues are being addressed, could be removed from the schedule or shifted to non-prime broadcast time. The preponderant service mode of communication, which obliges the media to worship at the altar of profit and consumerism, often tends to vitiate the ideals of social responsibility. The profit motive places the media at the mercy of big businesses (advertisers and conglomerates) while consumerism often obliges the media to pander to low public taste, under the pretext that they are giving the public what they want.

The cardinal responsibility of broadcasting is to distribute informative, educative and entertaining information to their audience to make informed choices, facilitate the formation of public opinion by providing an independent forum of debate; and enable the people to shape the conduct of government by articulating their views (Curran 1991:29). As a creative medium, characterised by professionalism, choice and innovation, the media serve the interest of the general public. Their ability to reach their audience simultaneously avails citizens the opportunity information dissemination and reception. It also affords individuals the opportunity to share their opinion and participate in discussions in their environment. It is expected to influence society positively, setting the agenda for the social, cultural, economic, political and technological development of a nation, for the public good.

By means of broadcasting, every Nigerian is expected to partake in sharing of ideas and experiences that will

enrich his or her life and help him or her live in a complex, dynamic and humane society, as envisaged in Chapter two of the *1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria* as amended. Every station exists to inform, educate and entertain the general public. Also performs the functions of socializing and sensitizing the citizens for activities considered necessary at a given time. The motives for establishing broadcasting stations in Nigeria are concern for public interest, profit-making consideration, power and influence, and propagation of knowledge (Okenwa, 1998; Udejah, 2011).

Revenue sources for a broadcast organisation is based on four conventional sources; advertisement, individual or organisation's donation, government subvention and licence sales (Okenwa, 1998; Udejah, 2011). This paper, therefore, examined the effect of the increasing commercial drive of broadcast industries on public service programming and schedules and explore strategies to help broadcast organisations to continue to serve its audience without jeopardising its public service broadcasting mandate.

This paper is anchored on two theories; social responsibility and democratic participation theories.

Social Responsibility Theory

This theory has a wide range of applications since it covers several kinds of private print and public corporations of broadcasting, which are answerable through various kinds of democratic procedures to the society. According to Okenwa (2002, p.4), the theory focuses on the consequences of the media and the attendant activities on the society, and places demands of responsibility on the operators without undermining the importance of freedom.

It is not in doubt that the mass media owe the society some responsibilities in packaging of contents. According to Schramm (1979) and Asemah (2013, p. 148), such responsibilities include:

- a. The media as watchmen,
- b. The mass media widen horizon,
- c. The media raise aspirations,
- d. The media can focus attention (agenda setting),
- e. can create a climate for development,

f. partake in the decision process and,

g. The media touch all facets of human existence. This theory was adopted because it stresses the negative implications of sacrificing the satisfaction of consumers' interest on the altar of economic goals.

Democratic Participant Media Theory

This theory according to Dennis McQuail in 1987 supports the principles of democratisation of the media for the purpose of accessibility by every citizen. The main thrust is the need for popular participation and plurality in the ownership and access to the media. The democratic participant media theory surfaced, when high technological development made investment in the media increasingly higher and consequently more commercially inclined. The ever-increasing cost of investment in the mass media meant that fewer people could contemplate the venture.

The democratic participant theory stresses the need for access and right to communication by all (Yarosan and Asemah, 2008). McQuail (1987) outlined the basic assumptions of the theory to include:

- a. Individual citizens and minority groups have right of access to media and rights to be served by the media based on their determination of needs;
- b. The organisation and content of the media should not be subjected to centralised, political or state bureaucratic controls;
- c. The media should exist primarily for their audiences and not for the media organisations, professionals or of the client of the media;
- d. Groups, organisations and local communities should have their own media;
- e. Small scale, interactive and participative media forms are better than large scale, one-way and professionalised media; and
- f. Certain social needs relating to mass media are adequately expressed through individual consumer demands, not through the state and its major institutions. This theory is appropriate for this work because it explains the role of the mass media to further public interest.

Broadcasting Objectives and Commercialisation in Nigeria

Broadcasting in Nigeria is guided by the broad objectives, which are in line with the fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy, as set out in chapter two of the 1999 Constitution. Broadcasting is expected to provide an efficient, professional and comprehensive service to the entire people of the Federal Republic of Nigeria based on national objectives and aspirations. Specifically, objectives of broadcasting in Nigeria include: social objectives, cultural objectives, economic objectives, political objectives, technological objectives, professional objectives (National Broadcasting Commission, 2010, p.7-11).

Commercialisation of the broadcast media in Nigeria is a product of the policy of privatisation and commercialisation of public enterprises of Decree 25 promulgated and implemented by the Federal Government of Nigeria under General Ibrahim Babangida. The objectives of the programme of privatisation and commercialisation include:

1. To restructure and rationalize the public sector to lessen the dominance of unproductive investments in that sector
2. To re-orientate the enterprises for privatisation and commercialisation towards a new horizon of performance, improvement, viability and overall efficiency.
3. To ensure positive returns on public sector investment in commercialised sector.
4. To check the present absolute dependence of commercially oriented enterprises on the treasury for funding and to encourage their approach to the stock market.
5. To initiate the process of gradual cession to the private sector of their operations and other socio-economic factors best performed by the private sector (Fagbo, 1989).

Zayyard (1992) distinguished between fully commercialised and partially commercialised enterprises and noted:

“enterprises to be partially commercialised would be expected to operate like fully commercialised ones in terms of better management and profit orientation. But because of the public nature of services provided by these enterprises and in other to keep the prices as low as possible for the public good, government would still provide financial grants for the capital projects of the partially commercialised enterprises”.

The enterprises would however, be expected to earn enough revenue to cover their operating cost. They will enjoy considerable operation autonomy and have the power to operate on strict commercial basis.

At the time, the Nigerian Television Authority (NTA) came under the category of partially commercialised enterprises. The Memorandum of Understanding to this effect was signed between NTA and the Technical Committee on Privatization and Commercialisation (TCPC) on July 7, 1992. NTA therefore, is expected to operate as a purely commercial enterprise and subject to the general regulatory powers of the government, may fix prices, and charges for goods and services, provide capital assets, borrow money, issue debenture, stocks, sue and be sued in its corporate name (Zayyard, 1992)

The immediate and most direct consequence of this new status of NTA, Kolade (1989) observes is that television will become a commercialised business, and regarding the effects on the social service function of television, he asserts, it must continue to render a number of social services, albeit, as a business enterprise. The implication of this commercial status is that all activities will come to be assessed on the basis of business criteria (Kolade, 1989).

One of the arguments advanced in favour of commercial broadcasting, Nwosu (1990) recalls, is that it will help to advance the educational and developmental objectives of the country through diversifying and extending broadcasting services beyond the urban and elite circles. Commercialisation was equally adjudged to bring about competition in the drive to satisfy consumers and

therefore engender professionalism in the industry. Another argument is that commercialisation of the mass media will, lead to gradual depoliticization of the media and engendering professionalism (Oso, 1990). While many nurse the fear that commercialisation will have some obvious implications, some assert that commercial outlook in NTA is an age-long affair. One time Director General of NTA, Mallam Ibrahim (1992) concurs when he said “although the authority was conceived primarily as a public service outfit, the decree establishing it in 1977 confers on it the right to canvas for broadcast commercials.” The enabling decree as quoted by Ibrahim (1992) states:

“the programme broadcast by the authority or on its behalf may be sponsored and may broadcast in consideration of payment by persons requiring such sponsored programmes, advertisements and announcement to be broadcast”.

The Technical Committee on Privatisation and Commercialisation agreement stipulates that one of the reasons for commercialisation is to make the organisation self-sustaining. Other reasons are drastic reduction in government spending due to escalating cost of equipment and spare parts, nearly all of which are imported and the high cost of domestic inputs such as electricity, telephone, vehicle, among other consideration. Advancing reasons for charging money in NTA, Ibrahim (1992) said the original target of “Let Them Pay” was the organised private sector particularly the multinational which announce their annual general meetings in newspapers and published their accounts soon after”. The new commercial posture of the broadcast media poses a great challenge on either the organisation or its consumers. The challenge of survival, growth and sustainability go for the establishment while that of ability to pay rests on consumers. This brings us to the fact that commercialisation has made broadcast media services go for the highest bidder, the rich controlling or brokering information in Nigeria. Whoever pays, controls in line with the widely used saying “he who pays the piper dictates the tune”. Sajo (1990), agreed with the above assertion when he said “television being a highly

and costly medium of advertising therefore, may attract only the wealthiest advertisers of firms with large publicity and advertising budgets.

Commenting on the twin concept of privatisation and commercialisation, Audu (1993) observes that what the advocates of private media fail to understand is that television is supposed to be a public utility services and not profit oriented. He decries the privatisation of the electronic media stressing that emphasis would be shifted to profit-making.

The objectives of the deregulation of the electronic media as enumerated by Adaba (1993) include:

- a) To enable broadcasting play a greater role in ensuring the accountability of government media to the citizens of Nigeria.
- b) To promote plurality of opinions across age, sex, socio-economic and geo-political barriers and so sustain the country’s democratic structure.
- c) To inject massive life-saving capital into the industry.
- d) To provide market place for goods, services and ideas.
- e) To increase and improve career opportunities and job satisfaction for talents and professionalism in the broadcasting industry.
- f) To be an honest vehicle for social engineering and the realisation of a strong united Nigeria.

One would but only imagined if the above objectives been fully realised with the economic inclination of the broadcast media. Harrison, (2006, p.100) captured news commercialisation as an economic process of ‘commodification’ whereby media audience are primarily seen as consumers. This economic rationalisation of broadcasting has been aggravated by the fragmentation of the mass audiences as consumers. Lacy in McManus (2009, p.221) states that “the growth of alternative information and advertising sources in the form of cable television and “the growth of public (stock) ownership of news media” are factors that have boosted commercialisation of news. However, Betiang, (2004) argued that commercialisation in Nigeria has

helped provide balance, and strengthen programming, and in many ways refined programming on public stations and, at the same time, widened the public sphere. These claims seem to imply that the liberalisation of broadcasting has helped to further the ethos of public service broadcasting in Nigeria for the common good and interest of the people. Thus, commentators of neo-liberal economic persuasion posit that only free markets can guarantee diversity of expression and open debates (Hutchins, 1947). They further argue that the media must be free to operate as an open market, where the public ultimately decide what to read, listen to and view, free from any form of state interference.

However, the problem that comes with the liberalisation of media ownership is that the high level of capitalisation in most sectors of the modern media restricts market entry to powerful capitalist interests (Curran, 1991). In short, commercialisation of broadcasting produces media oligopoly and conglomerates which control the distribution of information and ideas (Curran, 1991). The result is that, in the commercial media, news and information become a commodity to be bought and sold and only those with the means can afford to do so. Thus, with commercial broadcasting, news, current affairs, and educational programmes are no longer the main reason for the media's existence, but are seen as mere additions on the schedules aimed at creating a supportive environment for advertisements (Kurpius, 2003).

In addition, with advertising as the backbone of commercial broadcasting, media products such as programming are tilted towards satisfying their sponsors, and away from the people (Golding and Murdock, 2000). This approach presents the audience to be classified as a commodity to be bought at a price determined by the size and social composition of the audience that the particular programme attracts. Thus, Seaton (2000) argues that, with commercial broadcasting, broadcasters do not sell programmes to audience but audiences to advertisers.

Determining Factors of Mass Media Content and Messages

Mass media content is a product of the interaction between different interests within mass media, different

roles of mass media, different sources of information, and different interests of groups outside mass media organization (McCullagh, 2002; Shoemaker, 1991; Press Freedom, 1997; Koltsova, 2001).

Shoemaker (1991) builds the hierarchical model of sources that influence content of mass media on three levels: individual level, media routines level, and organizational level. On individual level, content of media messages is affected by communicators' personal backgrounds, experiences, attitudes, values, and beliefs and by communicators professional backgrounds, roles, ethics, and power within the organization. "Organizations must 'routinize' work in order to control it" (Shoemaker, 1991, p. 97). These routines affect individual communicators and their way of working.

On the organizational level, content is affected by the economic goals of a media organization, its structure, internal policies, internal control, and organizational roles. The goals of an organization are determined by the owners of the organization. There are also effects on content of mass media messages from non-organizational levels: extra-media level and ideological level.

On the extra-media level, content is affected by sources of information, revenue sources, other social institutions, economic environment, and technology. Ideology addresses issues of accepted and non-accepted behaviour, determines spheres of consensus and deviance.

Public Interest and Mass Media

When discussing the public interest, social scientists and policy makers refer to absolutely different things. The diversity of definitions of the public interest is caused by the presence of different layers of meaning. Napoli identifies three levels of the meaning: conceptual, operational, and applicational. The conceptual level is the broadest one and deals with how the public interest is defined in general. On the operational level specific principles are defined to constitute what is now defined as the public interest. On the applicational level principles of the operational level are transformed into actions and regulations (Napoli, 2006).

Simone (2005) identifies different levels of meaning: process, principle and policy. Process refers to the methods used to define what the public interest is. Principle refers to the concepts that are seen as constituting the public interest. Policy refers to the specific policies regulations, norms that are introduced to serve the public interest. Simone (2005) argues that ambiguity in defining the public interest is not a consequence of different layers of meaning, but that it results from a different vision of process.

Both conceptual and process levels give broad perspective on the public interest and define other levels. They give theoretical vision of the public interest, provide ways to approach it. Croteau and Hoynes (2001) identify two perspectives on mass media– market model and public sphere model – which affect the way the public interest is seen.

In the market model of media, content of media is seen as any other product. The interests of the public are served by demand and supply. The public interest is what public is interested in and what it demands. Audience of mass media is seen as consumers. The primary goal of media is to generate profit, and profit is a measure of success. Competition between media companies should ensure that the public interest is served properly.

The main assumption of the public sphere model is market's inability to meet the society's needs. Based on the characteristics of the public sphere model, Croteau and Hoynes, (2001) see the public sphere on a macro level as a social discourse that enables the circulation of ideas and knowledge, thereby ensuring the successful socialization of individuals into society. Mass media are seen as capable of affecting people's behaviour (Lippmann, 1965). Having an effect on the public, media organizations should "promote active citizenship, education, and social integration" through their messages (Croteau & Hoynes, 2001, p. 37).

On the application level or the level of policy making, the market model approach to media would ensure the market operates without regulations in order to serve the public interest. Any regulation will interfere with the natural interaction of supply and demand. As the market

is oriented to make profits, and profits are associated with volumes of products (except very expensive products to satisfy desires of just few individuals), mass media may serve wants of the majority. Public interest is defined in majoritarian way (McQuail,1992,p. 22). This is seen as one of the imperfections of the market: media firms make profits but the public's demand is not fully satisfied.

In addition to the imperfection, in the market model, mass media fail to serve needs of some people due to double product – content for people and attention of these people to advertisers. As the main source of revenue for several types of mass media is advertisement placement, mass media are "under pressures for maximizing profits" (Bagdikian, 1997, p. 199). Bogart (1995, p.108) indicates that "media formulate their content to maximize advertising income". This reinforces the emphasis on addressing the needs of majority. Studies show that competition on the media market does not always lead to diversity. Moreover, high level of competition may result in decreasing of diversity (Hollifield, 2006, Park, 2005).

Diversity refers to different levels. On the level of the media market it refers to the presence of different media channels, on the level of channel it refers to the presence of different types of programs, and on the level of content it refers to the presence of different points of view on issues. All types of diversity are important to serve the public interest. They ensure that the interests of different audiences are addressed.

In the public sphere model audiences are seen as citizens who are encouraged by media messages to learn about their world. The public interest is served through the presence of "diverse, substantive, and innovative content, even if not always popular" (Croteau & Hoynes, 2001, p.37). As the market economy cannot ensure that the public interest is served, regulations are needed to protect the public interest.

Media in public sphere model, according to Croteau & Hoynes (2001), should be characterized by diversity, innovation, substance and independence. Innovation means creative and fresh content rather than the presence

of new technologies. Substantial media messages are those that address significant issues, educate audiences, and promote participation in social life. To meet the fourth criterion, content should be independent from corporate and governmental interests. Government and other organizations should not limit the range of presented perspectives on issues.

According to McCullagh (2002) mass media organizations should meet the following criteria to serve the public: 1) mass media messages should be available to all members of society: there should be no limitations of access to mass media messages based on race, age, education, wealth, and other characteristics of individuals; 2) mass media messages should address different interests of audiences; 3) mass media messages should provide the public with education; 4) mass media messages should contribute to building a sense of community.

On Simone (2005) level of policy, the public sphere model would ensure that the media market is regulated in order to address the different interests of different people, form social (cultural and national) identity and protect audiences from harmful content. In the second model the public interest is determined not according to the will of the public, but according to some (absolute) standards and values. On the operational and the application levels this will lead to a problem of identifying these standards. Usually, they are identified in accordance to a dominant ideology.

Conclusion/ Recommendations

The audience factor is the most important single factor in the broadcast industry. Not only do they determine what goes into the media but they consume the product. One of the methods of generating revenue is through advertisement refers to as commercial. Commercials are targeted at the audience. The broadcast media woo the audience for the advertisers who pay for the use of the audience.

Contemporary broadcast industry can balance the economic equation by satisfying the interest of the audience without yielding to advertisers' influences to

the detriment of the audience. Therefore, the broadcast organisations have to respect the consumers' right.

Advertisement and entertainment should not compete for space with news and current affairs. It is obvious because public broadcasting is positioned to be self-sustaining and revenue-generating; they are forced to generate revenue through advertisement. The result is that, in order to attract advertisers to the station, little space is left for current affairs and educative programmes.

Commercial broadcasters should carry public service programmes so that they can reach a larger audience, and justify their exclusive use of the limited public frequency.

There is need for audience research as a way of testing their acceptability of the commercial posture of the broadcasting media against satisfying consumers' interest and enlighten them on the desirability or otherwise of generating revenue to keep the station afloat.

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